

Building Secure and Resilient Intercontinental Connectivity for European Research and Education

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This summary document outlines the strategic vision, analysis, and recommendations drawn up by GÉANT for the provision of resilient intercontinental connectivity to support research and education (R&E) between Europe and other world regions. It draws on the experience of the EU-funded GN5-IC1 project [1], which has published its findings on the subjects of European digital sovereignty and security of intercontinental connectivity needs in its final deliverable *GN5-IC1 D2.2 Resilience in Intercontinental Research Networks White Paper* [2]. The present document is intended to publicly disseminate some of these results, along with some additional reflections.

Research today is global, data-intensive, and highly collaborative, as demonstrated by the fact that approximately 25% of traffic on the GÉANT network originates or has its destination outside Europe [1]. This requires secure, high-capacity global links to enable scientific collaboration, data exchange, and innovation across borders. At global scale, research traffic is carried almost exclusively by subsea telecommunication cable systems, making these assets as critical for R&E connectivity as they are to the Internet, and a fundamental element in the strategic approach to the delivery of intercontinental connectivity set out in this paper.

The criticality of the subsea communication infrastructure is well recognised by the European Commission, which in February 2025 published the *EU Action Plan on Cable Security* [3], a comprehensive strategy created to protect critical submarine cable infrastructures. More recently, this has been addressed in the work of the Submarine Cable Infrastructure Expert Group as set out in its report on *Security and Resilience of EU Submarine Cable Infrastructures* [4]. This criticality is widely acknowledged, even beyond GÉANT and the EC, and is producing an increase in investments in this area – including the European Commission’s Global Gateway initiatives [5] – several of which GÉANT is already involved in.

These substantial investments being channelled into building new subsea cable systems [6] present opportunities for the R&E networking community to participate in these projects from the outset, securing supply and shaping project outcomes to ensure value for the R&E sector is maximised. In this respect, GÉANT has adopted an approach whereby, driven by the EU’s digital sovereignty considerations, its technical expertise and established regional relationships are combined with blended financing mechanisms with the involvement of EU financial institutions (e.g. EIB) to mobilise European private sector investment. Some examples of these collaborations are initiatives such as BELLA [7], Medusa [8] and Blue-Raman [9].

On the strength of their first-hand experience in delivering such initiatives, a cross-functional team of experts from GÉANT have undertaken a comprehensive intercontinental connectivity analysis that takes into account the landscape and market; European drivers for intercontinental connectivity; past, current and projected network traffic forecasts; tax, legal and regulatory implications; and some of the risks affecting prospective investments and potential mitigations.

Some of the key elements highlighted by this work are:

- **Research and Education Network (REN) Connectivity Landscape:** R&E networks operate as a federated global mesh of interlinked National and Regional RENs. These networks are increasingly adopting long-term ownership models (IRUs for spectrum or fibre) over short-term leases to ensure security of supply. Resiliency and uptime are key concerns.
- **Market Trends:** Subsea telecommunication cables investment is accelerating driven by surging Hyperscaler demand, aging infrastructure, and growing geopolitical risks. Ownership and routing are also changing to suit demand, with Hyperscaler systems taking the lion's share of new and planned systems in all geographies. Sovereignty concerns drive EU initiatives such as Global Gateway [5] aimed at securing strategic routes and control over the supply chain.
- **Funding:** Horizon Europe and the Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument (NDICI) – Global Europe are deemed the most suitable EU funding mechanisms to support intercontinental connectivity projects for the benefit of European R&E users.
- **Traffic Forecasts:** Average R&E traffic between GÉANT and other world regions has shown a historical growth level of approximately 30%. While this growth has declined in the most recent years, peak demand between Europe and other major regions (e.g., USA, Asia-Pacific) is still expected to reach terabit levels by 2033, requiring scalable solutions.
- **Risks:** Key risks include infrastructure availability and accessibility, regulatory complexity, long-term financial exposure, security, and geopolitical instability. Mitigation requires strong governance, growing legal expertise, and diversified routes. Policymaker support is also essential to ensure infrastructure remains accessible to the public with private cables becoming more common.

GÉANT aims to position itself as an indispensable and trusted partner of both the EC and global research and education networks, enabling European researchers and academics to seamlessly collaborate at a global scale while supporting European data sovereignty, security and confidentiality. To consolidate GÉANT's approach to intercontinental connectivity, three Pillars have been defined to support this vision and guide investments:

- **Pillar 1: Serving the needs of the European R&E Community.** Ensuring that investment meets the needs of GÉANT Member RENs, European big science infrastructures and collaborations.
- **Pillar 2: Global Collaboration.** Covering collaboration with other regions and focusing on the development of R&E Networking globally.
- **Pillar 3: European Autonomy.** Ensuring an appropriate level of control by GÉANT over intercontinental connectivity in support of European digital sovereignty.

While all investments should aim at reinforcing at least one of the above Pillars, all three Pillars ultimately feed into GÉANT's overarching objective defined by Pillar 1, which is to serve the European R&E community.

With this new systematic approach, GÉANT is determining the suitability of intercontinental connectivity (IC) investment opportunities, ensuring alignment with the GÉANT Association's strategy [10] and governance and continuing to support the evolving needs of the European research community. Long-term investment into connectivity to Singapore, a critical regional hub, as well as the purchase of spectrum to North America and participation in the Medusa and Blue-Raman initiatives are practical examples of how GÉANT's IC vision is being implemented.

Finally, an implementation roadmap has been drawn up that will guide prioritisation of future investments to ensure sufficient capacity and diversity are available for European R&E needs. This roadmap identifies projects of interest and that are functional to the delivery of the above-mentioned vision. Figure 1 below shows the most current version of the roadmap.

Figure 1: Intercontinental Connectivity Implementation Roadmap

In addition to the past and ongoing projects mentioned above, work in the context of Medusa is actively underway on connectivity through Aqaba to add an important node on routes between Europe, the Eastern Mediterranean, Africa and Asia. Looking further ahead, GÉANT's intercontinental focus will turn towards the coast of West Africa. Further connectivity from India to Singapore and from Europe via Djibouti to East and South Africa will be pursued in the near term as part of the Blue-Raman initiative.

Planned routes over the longer term include redundancy for South America to complement BELLA connectivity; increased connectivity to Asia via West Africa; and connectivity to Antarctica, supporting scientific efforts in one of the planet's most remote and connectivity-constrained environments. Further connectivity to Canada and Japan also features, in alignment with the vision of the Polar Connect initiative [11] pioneered by NORDUnet that aims to open up new collaboration opportunities across the Arctic.

Achieving this ambitious plan will require continued joint efforts and collaboration between the European and global Research and Education Networking communities, policymakers, financial institutions, and private sector players, to ensure that research networks remain active and influential in this technology space.

Glossary

EC	European Commission
EIB	European Investment Bank
EU	European Union
GN5-FPA	The GN5 (GÉANT Network 5) Framework Partnership Agreement, a 7-year strategic framework that outlines the overall direction, objectives, and impacts of individual projects within that timeframe as part of the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme
GN5-IC1	GÉANT Network 5, Phase 1, International Connectivity 1, a project funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101086099 and one of the projects implementing the actions defined in the GN5-FPA
IC	Intercontinental Connectivity
IRU	Indefeasible Right of Use
NDICI	Neighbourhood, Development and International Cooperation Instrument
R&E	Research and Education
REN	Research and Education Network

References

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[Resource available to project participants only]
- [3] *EU Action Plan on Cable Security* <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/joint-communication-strengthen-security-and-resilience-submarine-cables>
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- [6] 'Building Tomorrow's Internet: A 2025 Update on Cable Investment', *Telegeography* <https://blog.telegeography.com/building-tomorrows-internet-an-update-on-new-cable-investment>
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